

THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: MATERIAL DEVELOPMENTS FOR AEROSPACE APPLICATIONS, INCORPORATION OF A FUNCTIONAL TIE LAYER

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ABSTRACT

A tie layer is introduced at the surface of chemically resistant semi-crystalline thermoplastic composites to improve the adhesion strength between these substrates and coatings or adhesives. This allows for coating of carbon fabric reinforced poly(phenylene sulphide) without a rigorous pre-treatment. In addition, this tie layer can be used to promote adhesive joining of dissimilar materials such as thermoset composites and metals, allowing for the integration of multiple materials in one application. This paper presents these findings. Finally, some examples of the incorporation of an extra functionality are provided.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites are gaining importance in various structural light-weight applications due to their combination of specific mechanical properties and ease of processing, i.e. thermoforming, thermoplastic welding. Applications include automotive, oil&gas, civil infrastructure and aerospace. Exemplary applications in the latter field are the fixed wing leading edge on the A380, manufactured by Fokker Aerostructures, made from TenCate CETEX[®] glass fabric reinforced PPS. Another typical example includes clips to join the fuselage, frames and stringers in the A350. The amount of these clips adds up to a few thousand parts per aircraft. These clips are manufactured from carbon fabric reinforced PPS, and selected for reasons of mechanical performance and the ability to produce a large amount of these materials. These and other typical examples are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Typical examples of CETEX® aerospace applications.

The Range of Aerospace grade CETEX® materials include matrix systems such as poly(phenylene sulphone) (PPS), poly(ether ketone ketone) (PEKK), poly(ether ether ketone) (PEEK) and poly(ether imide) (PEI); all reinforced with carbon or glass fibers.

These materials are used for their combination of (thermo-)mechanical performance, inherent good fire, smoke and toxicity properties and inherent chemical resistance to a wide variety of fluids.

However, the good chemical resistance has a drawback as well, the interface is difficult to bond to, which requires a robust pre-treatment prior to for example coating or adhesive bonding.

This paper presents a way to modify the composite surface by the addition of a tie layer, which improves the interface and allows for a good interface to other dissimilar materials without extensive pre-treatment. Following applications are envisaged:

Coating. This pre-treatment omits an extensive pre-treatment, and have a robust process and a good interface between coatings and the substrate

Adhesive joining. Thermoplastic substrates are typically joined by welding or riveting. However with the increased use of dissimilar materials in aircraft, adhesive bonding of thermoplastic composites to thermosets and/or aluminium would be beneficial. The use of a tie layer enables adhesive joining of these substrates

Incorporation of functionality. Such a surface top-layer can be used to incorporate various other functionalities, including overmoulding of different thermoplastics onto a C-PPS substrate.

2 APPROACH

The introduction of a tie layer originates from co-extrusion of dissimilar thermoplastic materials with a low compatibility. The addition of a tie layer ensures a good bond between the two materials; it acts as an intermediate, with a good compatibility to both materials. The same principle is applied here. During the consolidation of the laminates a tie layer is added, which has a good interaction with the composite material. After processing, such as thermoforming, this tie layer forms the interface to the coating or adhesive.

As substrate material carbon fabric reinforced PPS was chosen, as this used in a variety of exterior applications, requiring coating applications. In addition PPS poses the largest challenge for coating and adhesive bonding.

The tie layer was developed in such a way that that is has good compatibility to PPS and to epoxy based materials, which form the basis of a variety of coatings and adhesives and is able to withstand the higher processing temperatures needed to process these type of thermoplastic composites.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following paragraphs, the processability and resulting properties for coatings, adhesive joints are presented.

3.1 Processing

A typical process includes stacking of the prepreg materials and consolidate these in a press to form larger laminates. From these laminates blanks are cut, thermoformed, trimmed, and in case of exterior applications, coated.

A schematic representation of the thermoforming process is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Thermoform process from a pre-consolidated laminate.

To incorporate the tie layer, an additional thin layer is added during the consolidation, which interdiffuses in the PPS matrix to form an interphase. After thermoforming, the coating is applied. During cure of the coating, the remainder of the tie layer partially diffuses into the coating. This process is schematically depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the tie layer adhesive mechanism during the process steps. Tie layer after press consolidations (upper image). Application and cure of coating or adhesive (center image). Fracture surface in case of adhesive application (lower image).

3.2 Coating

The results for the coating systems are provided in the table below, showing the requirements the results for cleaned but untreated C/PPS and for cleaned but untreated C/PPS including a tie layer. Cleaning was done using isopropanol to remove grease and dust contamination.

		Requirements	C-PPS	Tie layer
1 mm squares	Dry*	0	1	0
	Wet**	1	1	0
2 mm squares	Dry*	0	2-4	0
	Wet**	1	1-2	0

Table 1. Results of cross hatch test after coating of a carbon fabric reinforced PPS substrate. *Test of unconditioned laminates. **tested after immersion in a water bath for 14 days.

The cross-hatch test was performed according to ISO 2409, and provides a rating from 0 to 5. 0 meaning good adhesion and 5 complete delamination of the coating. It can be seen that the addition of a tie layer results in a good adhesion of the coating on the C-PPS substrate without extensive pre-treatment.

3.3 Adhesive Bonding

The adhesion to an epoxy adhesive (FM300) was tested using lap-shear testing. For this, two substrates of C-PPS were joined using three routes:

1. The tie layer was used to weld the C-PPS specimens to each other, below the melting point of PPS. This welding process was not optimized but provides adhesion with a lap-shear strength of around 9 MPa.

2. Samples with a tie layer were bonded with an epoxy adhesive. The resulting lap-shear strength reached approximately 20 MPa, with a predominantly cohesive failure. It must be noted that the bond line was very thin, which is not optimal for lap-shear tests.
3. C-PPS without tie layer was slightly sanded and cleaned. The adhesive strength was close to zero as it fell apart prior to testing.

Set	σ_L [Mpa]	Failure Mode	Remarks
1. Welding of tie layer	9.31 (± 0.53)	Predominantly at fiber surface	Very thin bondline (close to 0mm)
2. Tie layer + epoxy adhesive	19.40 (± 0.61)	Cohesive failure	Very thin bondline (close to 0mm)
4. C-PPS	0	100% adhesive	No adhesion

Table 2. Results of lap shear tests of C-PPS specimens .1. Welding of two specimens below the melting point of C-PPS. 2. Adhesively bonded C-PPS with tie layer using FM300. 3. Adhesively bonded C-PPS without tie layer using FM300.

Figure 4. Failure modes of lap shear tests. 1. Welding of two specimens below the melting point of C-PPS. 2. Adhesively bonded C-PPS with tie layer using FM300. 3. Adhesively bonded C-PPS without tie layer using FM300.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this experimental study, the incorporation of a tie layer to promote adhesion between coatings or adhesives and thermoplastic composites was studied. It was shown that the tie layer drastically improves the coating quality, while omitting the need for an extensive pre-treatment. The same approach can be taken for adhesively bonded joints, where the tie layer promotes the adhesion between the substrate and the adhesive.